

The Influence of Work Flexibility and Work Morale on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia

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KEYWORDS: Job Flexibility, Morale, Job Satisfaction and Performance.

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effect of work flexibility and work enthusiasm on employee performance through job satisfaction at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia. This study uses a quantitative approach with primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The number of samples is determined using the Slovin formula, so that from a total population of 328 employees, a sample of 180 respondents is obtained. The data analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the help of the LISREL 8.80 application. The results of the study indicate that: (1) work flexibility has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction; (2) work enthusiasm has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction; (3) work flexibility has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; (4) work enthusiasm does not affect employee performance; (5) job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance; (6) work flexibility and work enthusiasm directly or indirectly have a positive and significant effect on employee performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. Based on the research results, companies are advised to adjust flexible work systems and focus on aspects that increase job satisfaction, because this factor has been proven to have the most influence on performance.

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INTRODUCTION

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a crucial function within an organization, focused on the planning, development, and maintenance of human resources. Its goal is to improve employee performance and effectively achieve organizational goals. HRM encompasses various aspects such as recruitment, training, performance appraisal, compensation, and managing employee-management relationships. Proper human resource management significantly impacts company productivity, making employee performance key to organizational success.

Human Resource Management is a comprehensive process for managing and maximizing employee potential so that an organization can achieve its goals. Without employees, it is difficult for an organization to achieve its goals. Therefore, the achievement of organizational goals depends on the collaboration between interrelated organizational components. Therefore, it is crucial for organizations to have a sound strategy for recruiting and retaining employees. To improve this, companies are required to provide job satisfaction to each employee. By increasing employee job satisfaction, companies are expected to also improve employee performance.

Employee performance is the result of work that is assessed based on its quality and quantity, in accordance with standards set by the company. To achieve good performance, companies must provide comfort to employees and foster work enthusiasm. High work enthusiasm has the potential to increase productivity, innovation, and job satisfaction, thus contributing to the achievement of organizational goals. Research shows that employees who feel motivated and have high morale tend to demonstrate better performance. Employee performance is a key factor in determining the success of an organization. Without optimal performance, company goals

will be difficult to achieve. This also applies to PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia, particularly in the Department Unit, which is facing various challenges in improving employee performance. Although the company has implemented various policies, such as work supervision, to increase productivity, several obstacles still hinder the achievement of maximum work results. Some of the emerging problems include declining employee motivation to achieve and a lack of discipline in completing tasks on time. Furthermore, employee work quality is considered low due to minimal preparation before starting work. Employees also tend to procrastinate, indicating a lack of work enthusiasm and a low level of responsibility for assigned tasks. The following is data on PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia monthly product targets and realizations.

Based on data, it can be seen that the data shows that PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia in the Dept Unit section, experienced a significant decline in production targets, in the last few months every month, which can be said to have achieved the target if the target is realized to reach 100% according to the predetermined target, it can be seen in January The production target was set at 850,000 units, but the realization only reached 765,000 units, which means there was a decrease of 10%. In February the production target was set at 840,000 units, but the realization only reached 739,200 units, which means there was a decrease of 12%. In March the production target was set at 800,000 units, but the realization only reached 712,000 units, which means there was a decrease of 11%. In April the production target was set at 790,000 units, but the realization only reached 679,400 units, which means there was a decrease of 14%. In May, the production target was set at 750,000 units, but only 660,000 units were produced, a 12% decrease. In June, the production target was set at 870,000 units, but only 739,500 units were produced, a 15% decrease. In July, the production target was set at 750,000 units, but only 622,500 units were produced, a 17% decrease. In August, the production target was set at 700,500 units, but only 560,400 units were produced, a 20% decrease. In September, the production target was set at 670,800 units, but only 556,764 units were produced, a 17% decrease.

It can be concluded that the decline in production targets at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia is due to poor employee performance. One possible contributing factor is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling that arises when employees feel their needs and expectations are met in the work environment. Furthermore, a study (Ningsih, 2019) states that a lack of incentives or rewards for employees can lead to decreased work enthusiasm, thus reducing productivity and affecting employee performance. Furthermore, a lack of work flexibility causes many employees to feel tied to work hours, which reduces work-life balance. Several other factors contribute to decreased employee performance, including low work morale. Some employees exhibit decreased work enthusiasm due to a lack of recognition and appreciation from management, which affects their performance. Employee performance is crucial because it serves as a benchmark for an employee's ability to complete assigned tasks.

Workplace flexibility refers to an organization's ability to support employees in managing their time and workspace while remaining focused on achieving work-related goals. In today's business environment, many companies are emphasizing employee flexibility to increase the level of overlap between work and personal life. Work flexibility can provide job satisfaction, reduce stress, and encourage better performance. The implementation of work flexibility at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia is one strategy that can improve employee performance and satisfaction. This can be seen in a scientific journal by management, business, and accounting students, written by (Findriyani & Parmin, 2021), entitled "The Effect of Self-Efficacy and Work Flexibility on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable (A Study of Employees of PT Sung Shim Internasional, Sempor Branch)," which states that work flexibility influences employee performance at PT Sung Shim Internasional, Sempor Branch. Meanwhile, a study in the Religion Education Social Laa Roiba Journal, written by (Alim & Prabowo, 2023), entitled "The Effect of Compensation and Work Flexibility on Performance Through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable for ShopeeFood Drivers in Sidoarjo," states that work flexibility has no significant effect on performance.

Work morale is also a crucial factor that can influence performance. Employees with high work morale tend to be more enthusiastic in completing their tasks, work responsibly, and contribute more optimally to the company. Work morale can be influenced by various factors, such as a conducive work environment, recognition for work achievements, and good relationships between superiors and subordinates. Employee morale is also a significant issue at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia. Several employees reported that the monotonous work environment, work pressure, and work-related stress are significant. High work motivation, as well as minimal appreciation for their work results, reduce their work enthusiasm. Employees with low work enthusiasm tend to be less motivated to make good contributions, which ultimately has a negative impact on employee performance and company productivity. As can be seen in the Journal of Management, written by (Basri & Rauf, 2021) with the title "The Effect of Work Morale and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance," and it is stated that work morale has a direct and significant influence on performance. Meanwhile, in the Management Development and Applied Research Journal, written by (Zainuddin & Darman, 2020) with the title "The Effect of Work Morale, Leadership Style, and Work Ethic on Employee Performance at PT. Bank BRI Majene Branch," it is stated that work morale does not have a significant partial effect on performance.

In addition to flexibility affecting employee performance and work morale affecting employee performance, work flexibility and work morale also affect job satisfaction. As can be seen in the journal Accounting, Management, and Policy Planning, written by (Sofyan & Elmi, 2024) with the title "The Effect of Work Flexibility and Work Life Balance with Job Training as a Moderating Variable on Consultant Job Satisfaction in DKI Jakarta", and it is stated that Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. Meanwhile, in the Journal of Management and Business, written by (Sitorus & Siagian, 2023) with the title

"Workload and Work Flexibility on Job Satisfaction with Motivation as a Mediator", and it is said that Work Flexibility has no effect on Job Satisfaction. This can be seen in the Indonesian Business Journal, written by (Sidik & Kalimin, 2018) with the title "The Influence of Work Morale on Employee Job Satisfaction at the Konawe Regency Transportation Office," which states that Work Morale has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction. Meanwhile, in the Journal of Publication and Management Science and E-Commerce, written by (Purnomo Waluyo et al., 2023) with the title "The Influence of Work Morale, Work Environment, and Career Development on Employee Satisfaction at PT. Cipta Rimba Djaja," it is stated that Work Morale does not have a positive and significant effect on Satisfaction. Furthermore, job satisfaction also affects employee performance, as can be seen in the Journal of Non-Formal Education, written by (Suryawan & Salsabilla, 2022) with the title "The Influence of Job Satisfaction, Work Discipline, and Work Motivation on Employee Performance," which states that job satisfaction has an impact on employee performance. Meanwhile, in the Journal of Islamic Management and Economics, written by Basri & Rauf (2021), entitled "The Influence of Work Morale and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance," it was stated that Job Satisfaction does not significantly influence Employee Performance.

The three issues discussed, namely work flexibility, work morale, and job satisfaction, are interrelated and influence each other. For example, low work flexibility can reduce work morale, while low work morale can affect job satisfaction. Therefore, this study aims to explore the relationship between these three variables and their impact on employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia. Therefore, based on the explanations presented, the results of previous observations, and the available supporting data, the researchers are interested in conducting a study entitled: "The Influence of Work Flexibility and Work Morale on Employee Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management (HRM) is the process of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling all activities related to human resource management within an organization. Human Resource Management encompasses various aspects, such as recruitment, training, development, performance appraisal, compensation, and employee relations. Every agency always expects resources capable of working effectively and efficiently to achieve its stated goals (Sidik & Kalimin, 2018).

According to (Pahira & Rinaldy, 2023), human resources play a crucial role in every organization because achieving maximum organizational performance requires utilizing all available resources, including human resources. In the era of globalization, human resource management plays a highly strategic and decisive role.

Human Resources are an element that requires special attention within an organization. Human resources are the people who can carry out and determine organizational activities. Without human resources, an organization will not function properly. Therefore, human resources must be continuously developed and directed to achieve organizational goals (Anwar, 2022).

According to Iswandi (2021), human resources (HR) are a crucial factor within any organization or company. This is because an organization or company will not function without quality human resources. The role of human resource management is a key factor in transforming company management to achieve competitive advantage.

Human Resource Management (HR) plays a crucial role in ensuring a company achieves its strategic goals. To achieve this, HR Management is responsible for optimally managing employees so they can work effectively and contribute maximally to the company. These tasks focus not only on operational aspects but also include long-term planning aimed at creating added value for the company (Shabrina et al., 2023). From the above opinion, it is concluded that human resources (HR) play a crucial role in every organization and company. To achieve optimal performance and organizational goals, HR must be managed effectively and efficiently. In the era of globalization, HR management is a strategic factor determining organizational success. Without quality HR, an organization cannot function properly. Therefore, it is important to continue to develop and foster human resources in order to achieve competitive advantage and create value for the company.

Work Performance

Performance is a form of contribution made by employees to the company through achieving work results to achieve the company's mission. Performance encompasses both qualitative and quantitative work results obtained by employees while carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities assigned by Mangkunegara (Huda & Ekhsan, 2023).

Meanwhile, according to (Pahira & Rinaldy, 2023), performance is a measure of how well an employee performs compared to company standards over a specific period of time. Employee performance refers to an employee's contribution to the organization in terms of attendance, work quality, quantity of work, tenure, attitude toward the company environment, and so on. Numerous factors can influence employee performance, including work enthusiasm, work flexibility, and job satisfaction.

According to (Fangiziah et al., 2023), employee performance refers to the extent to which an organization succeeds or fails in carrying out its activities to achieve its stated goals, objectives, vision, and mission. Performance also encompasses the quality and quantity of work performed by individuals or groups in achieving these goals. As previously explained, employee performance plays a crucial role in a company's success. Companies need employees with strong skills and abilities.

According to (Lina, 2020), performance is the concrete actions demonstrated by each individual as a result of the work produced by employees in accordance with their role in the company. Employee performance is crucial for companies in achieving

their goals. Performance can be measured through employee morale. One factor driving optimal performance is providing compensation commensurate with employee performance in completing their tasks. However, in carrying out daily tasks, compensation issues often become a barrier within organizations.

According to (Busro, 2018:89) in (Atika & Mafra, 2020), performance is the work results achieved by employees, both individually and in groups, within an organization, in accordance with the authority and responsibilities granted by the organization in an effort to achieve the organization's vision, mission, and goals. This includes skills, perseverance, independence, and problem-solving abilities within legally stipulated deadlines and in accordance with morals and ethics.

From the above opinion, it can be concluded that performance is the level of success achieved by individuals in carrying out assigned tasks, in accordance with their expertise, experience, dedication, and available time. To achieve optimal results, the most crucial factor is human resources. Even if a plan is methodically and meticulously formulated, if the people implementing it are unqualified and lack enthusiasm, the plan will risk failure and not produce the desired results.

According to Mangkunegara (2017:67), as cited in (Atika & Mafra, 2020), factors influencing performance achievement include: ability and motivation. According to Bernadin and Russel (1993:383) as cited in (Husaini & Sutarna, 2021), several indicators are considered to influence employee performance, including quality, quantity, timeliness, and cost-effectiveness.

Work Satisfactio

According to Priansa (2014:291) in (Dewi & Nugroho, 2021), job satisfaction is an employee's emotional state toward their job, which relates to feelings of pleasure or displeasure between the employee and their work environment. Job satisfaction can influence motivation, productivity, and employee retention rates within an organization. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to have a higher commitment to the company and demonstrate better performance.

According to (Listyowati et al., 2021), job satisfaction can impact career success, commitment, and work quality. From this statement, it can be concluded that job satisfaction reflects a person's attitude toward the tasks and responsibilities they carry. Furthermore, job satisfaction helps create a positive work environment, where employees feel valued, supported, and more emotionally attached to the company.

Other research also reveals that job satisfaction reflects a person's positive attitude toward their work, where they feel happy, love, and truly enjoy what they do. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to demonstrate a high work ethic, have strong morals, and strive for good performance. They are also more disciplined, both in completing tasks, adhering to rules, and in time management. (Huda & Ekhsan, 2023). According to (Artameviah, 2022), job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude toward their work. This is influenced by interactions with coworkers and superiors, compliance with organizational rules and policies, achievement of performance standards, and often less-than-ideal working conditions, among other factors.

The impact of job satisfaction, as outlined by Griffin and Moorhead (2013:74) in Handoko (2020), is that job satisfaction impacts work performance and reduces absenteeism, contributes positively, and reduces employee turnover. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling or level of comfort an employee experiences with their job. It encompasses various aspects, such as the work environment, relationships with colleagues and superiors, and the fit between assigned tasks and personal expectations and values.

It can be concluded that job satisfaction is an individual's mood or attitude toward their work, which influences relationships with the work environment, coworkers, and superiors. Job satisfaction can improve career success, commitment, and work quality. The positive impacts of job satisfaction include reduced absenteeism and turnover rates, as well as increased employee contribution. In other words, job satisfaction is a crucial element influencing employee performance and well-being in the workplace.

Many experts define job satisfaction indicators, including Hasibuan (in Mardiana & Novalia, 2020), who proposed five indicators related to job satisfaction: Commitment, Ability and Honesty, Creativity, and the level of wages and salaries offered by the company must be in line with what employees are willing to pay..

Work Flexibility

Work flexibility is one aspect of increasing employee job satisfaction, particularly regarding work schedules, which impact performance improvement. Work flexibility allows employees to adapt to company-determined changes, enabling them to complete their work. Each employee can manage and be responsible for a single task (Ardiansyah, 2020), as described in (Sitorus & Siagian, 2023).

According to Atkinson and Hall (2011), work flexibility is defined as the ability of workers to regulate their work duration, either by working from any location or according to a predetermined schedule. Employees can choose their most productive time or adjust their schedule to accommodate other responsibilities, as long as work targets and responsibilities are met (Findriyani & Parmin, 2021). According to Hooks & Higgs (in Siskayanti & Sanica, 2022), work flexibility is the provision of flexible working hours for employees, allowing them to work shorter hours. This allows employees to have more free time, encouraging them to increase their creativity and advance the company.

According to Setyawan (2020), flexible working hours can increase employees' sense of responsibility within the company, thereby helping companies retain quality employees and reducing turnover rates. Work flexibility can influence employee comfort with their work, allowing them to work more freely and optimally, thus improving their performance (Siskayanti & Sanica, 2022).

Flexibility is the choice of where and when to work, both formally and informally, which provides employees with the

freedom to regulate the duration, time, and location of their work (Carlson et al., 2023). Work flexibility provides freedom in carrying out one's profession, allowing one to organize their schedule effectively, without burden, and without causing work stress (Mishra & Prasad, 2021).

According to Putri (2022), this flexibility refers to employees having the opportunity to determine and change their work schedules, thus enabling them to manage and balance work responsibilities with personal responsibilities. Work flexibility not only helps improve employee well-being but can also contribute to increased motivation and job satisfaction, as employees feel more empowered to manage their time and priorities. Ultimately, companies that implement work flexibility often benefit from increased productivity, higher employee loyalty, and better retention rates, as employees feel supported in maintaining a balance between their work and personal lives.

From the opinions above, it can be concluded that work flexibility, particularly in terms of schedule and workplace, plays a crucial role in increasing employee job satisfaction and accountability. By providing employees with the freedom to manage their time and workplace, companies can help them adapt to change, complete tasks better, and ultimately reduce turnover rates and retain quality employees. This flexibility allows employees to balance their work responsibilities with their personal lives.

According to Carlson et al. (in Lyonette & Crompton, 2020), schedule flexibility is a flexible work system arrangement in terms of time, place, and at a more informal level. Indicators of work flexibility include time flexibility, timing flexibility, and place flexibility..

Work Spirit

According to Hasibuan (in Basri & Rauf, 2021), work enthusiasm is a person's drive and commitment to carry out their duties well, with discipline, and a deep desire and interest in the work they do. By understanding human behavior, including the reasons behind a person's desire to work and the satisfaction they experience, a manager can be more effective in motivating their subordinates. Work enthusiasm drives someone to produce and be creative in their work. According to Chambers & Honeycutt (2009) in Hasibuan (2019), this enthusiasm is reflected in self-confidence, cheerfulness, discipline, and a willingness to complete assigned tasks.

Furthermore, according to Hadari Nawawi, high or positive work enthusiasm is a significant factor in increasing work productivity. This opinion aligns with the research findings of Maydina and Abdurrahman (2020) in Basri & Rauf (2021), which found that work enthusiasm plays a crucial role in positively increasing employee productivity.

According to (Riyanto & Anto, 2022), work enthusiasm reflects a person's efforts to carry out their tasks more diligently, so that work can be completed more quickly and better. With work enthusiasm, a person strives to improve the effectiveness and quality of work results.

According to (Syuhada & Amelia, 2021), work enthusiasm is the mental attitude of an individual or group that reflects the drive to work together and complete tasks on time, as well as being responsible for the work assigned. According to Tohardi, work enthusiasm is the ability of a group of people to work together actively and consistently in pursuit of a common goal.

Therefore, it can be said that work enthusiasm is the work atmosphere within an organization that reflects the mental attitude of individuals or groups within an organization that demonstrates a sense of enthusiasm in carrying out tasks/work and encourages them to work better and more productively. According to Nitisemito in (Syihab et al., 2020), indicators of work enthusiasm are as follows: Work Productivity, Attendance Level, and Peace of Mind at Work.

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a quantitative method. Quantitative research is a process of discovering knowledge that uses numerical data as a tool for analyzing information about what we want to know. Quantitative research, which is based on the assumption that a phenomenon can be classified and that the relationship between the phenomena is causal, allows researchers to focus on just a few variables (Djollong, 2019).

There are four variables in this study: two independent variables, one dependent variable, and one intervening variable. The first independent variable is Work Flexibility (X1). The second independent variable is Work Morale (X2). The dependent variable is Employee Performance (Y). The intervening variable is Job Satisfaction (Z). The following is the research framework used in this study based on the predetermined variables:

Picture 1. Research Disaign

Population and sample

According to Russia (Aribowo et al., 2020), a population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects possessing certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied, and then conclusions drawn. From the definition of population above, it can be concluded that a population is the total number of samples used in the research. In this study, the population taken was all 328 employees of PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia in the Unit.

According to Arikunto (Abadiyah, 2020), a sample is a portion of the population being studied and is called sample research if the researcher intends to generalize the results of the sample research. To determine the number of samples to be used in the research, the Slovin formula is used. Therefore, the sample used is 180

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Structural model analysis is conducted to determine whether there is a relationship between the latent variables in the research model. This process also aims to test the hypotheses proposed in the previous chapter. There are two types of tests conducted in this analysis: the overall model fit (GOF) test and the structural model fit test. The overall model fit test follows the same steps as the measurement model fit test. The results of this fit test are Goodness of Fit Statistics (GOF) values. Meanwhile, the structural model fit test is conducted by assessing the significance of the obtained coefficients.

Picture 2. Model Structure (Standardized)

Picture 3. Model Structure (T-Value)

Figures 2 and 3 show a relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The results of the significance test for the relationship between latent variables, or the path between two latent variables, show the resulting coefficient values along with the T-value. If the structural path has a T-value ≥ 1.96 , the path coefficient is considered significant. However, if the T-value is < 1.96 , the path coefficient is considered insignificant.

The Effect of Work Flexibility on Job Satisfaction

The first hypothesis (Ha) states that work flexibility influences job satisfaction. The figure shows that the calculated t-value is greater than the t-table, with a value of $5.46 > 1.96$, thus indicating significant significance. Therefore, work flexibility has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 1 (Ha) is accepted.

The Effect of Work Morale on Job Satisfaction

The second hypothesis (Ha) states that work morale influences job satisfaction. The figure shows that the calculated t-value is greater than the t-table value, at $3.31 > 1.96$, making it significant. Therefore, work morale has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, or in other words, Hypothesis 2 (Ha) is accepted.

The Effect of Work Flexibility on Employee Performance

The third hypothesis (Ha) states that work flexibility affects employee performance. The figure shows that the calculated t-value is greater than the t-table value, at $2.41 < 1.96$, making it significant. Therefore, work flexibility has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 3 (Ha) is accepted.

The Effect of Work Morale on Employee Performance

The fourth hypothesis (Ha) states that work morale has no effect on employee performance. The figure shows that the calculated t-value is smaller than the t-table value, at $1.09 < 1.96$, making it insignificant. Thus, work enthusiasm has been proven to have no positive and significant effect on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 4 (Ha) is rejected.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance.

The fifth hypothesis (Ha) states that job satisfaction influences employee performance. The figure shows that the calculated t-value is greater than the t-table value, at $3.52 < 1.96$, thus indicating a significant difference. Therefore, job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 5 (Ha) is accepted.

The Direct and Indirect Effects of Work Flexibility on Employee Performance

The sixth hypothesis (Ha) states that the direct effect of work flexibility on employee performance is $(0.31) 2100 = 9.61\%$. The indirect effect of work flexibility on employee performance through job satisfaction is $0.63 \times 0.59 \times 100 = 21.24\%$. The percentage results above indicate that work flexibility can improve employee performance both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction. Thus, job satisfaction is a mediating variable.

Direct and Indirect Effects of Work Morale on Employee Performance

The direct effect of work morale on employee performance is $(0.10)2100 = 1\%$. The indirect effect of work morale on employee performance is $0.34 \times 0.59 \times 100 = 20.06\%$. The percentage results above indicate that work morale can improve employee performance both directly and indirectly through job satisfaction. Therefore, job satisfaction is a mediating variable.

DISCUSSION

Work Flexibility Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Job Satisfaction

Based on the analysis of respondents' perceptions of the variable, Work Flexibility has an impact on Job Satisfaction. This can be seen from the calculated t-value, which is greater than the t-table, at $5.46 > 1.96$, thus Hypothesis 1 (Ha) is accepted. This means that the higher the perceived work flexibility of employees, the higher the level of job satisfaction. Flexibility indicators, according to Carlson (Lyonette & Crompton, 2020), include Time Flexibility, which allows employees to adjust their working hours, creating a better balance between work and personal life. Timing Flexibility provides flexibility in managing task schedules, which increases self-confidence and satisfaction. Meanwhile, Place Flexibility, although limited, provides the convenience of working from other locations when needed. Thus, the research results successfully prove that Work Flexibility has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia Dept Unit. The results of this study align with those of Sofyan & Elmi (2024), which found that flexible work practices significantly influence job satisfaction.

Work Morale has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Based on the analysis of respondents' perceptions of the variable, the Work Morale variable has an effect on job satisfaction. This can be seen from the calculated t-value, which is greater than the t-table, at $3.31 > -1.96$. Therefore, it can be concluded that the effect is significant. Thus, Work Morale is partially proven to have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, or in other words, Hypothesis 2 (Ha) is accepted. This means that higher work morale, higher employee job satisfaction. Indicators of work morale, according to Nitisemito (in Syihab et al., 2020), such as productivity, attendance, and work peace, also support this finding. Enthusiastic employees are more productive, attend regularly, and feel comfortable at work, thus being satisfied with their jobs. Thus, the research

findings demonstrate that Work Morale has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia Dept. Unit. These findings align with research conducted by Sriatun et al., 2020, which found that Work Morale practices significantly influence Job Satisfaction.

Work Flexibility Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Employee Performance

Based on the analysis of respondents' perceptions of the Work Flexibility variable, it impacts Employee Performance. This can be seen from the calculated T-value, which is greater than the T-table, at $2.41 > -1.96$. Therefore, it can be concluded that the effect is significant. Therefore, Work Flexibility is partially proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 3 (Ha) is accepted. Flexibility indicators, according to Carlson (Lyonette & Crompton, 2020), such as time flexibility, timing flexibility, and place flexibility, help employees adjust their work time and place, resulting in greater productivity and improved performance. Thus, the research findings demonstrate that Work Flexibility has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia Dept. Unit. These findings align with those of (Findriyani & Parmin, 2021), which found that Work Flexibility practices significantly impact employee performance.

Work Morale Does Not Have a Positive and Significant Effect on Employee Performance

Based on the analysis of respondents' perceptions, the variable Work Morale does not affect employee performance. This is evident from the calculated T-value, which is smaller than the T-table, at $1.09 > -1.96$. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant effect. Therefore, Work Morale is not proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 4 (Ha) is rejected. Work Morale does not have a direct positive effect on improving employee performance, but does have a positive effect through job satisfaction. According to Nitisemito (Syihab et al., 2020), indicators of work morale, such as work productivity, attendance, and calmness at work, do indicate enthusiasm, but they are insufficient without job satisfaction. This means that employees can be enthusiastic and show up on time, but without satisfaction, optimal performance is difficult to achieve. Thus, the research findings successfully prove that Work Morale does not have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. This finding is inconsistent with the research conducted by Basri & Rauf, (2021), stated that the practice of Work Morale significantly influences Employee Performance.

Job Satisfaction has a significant influence on Employee Performance.

Based on the analysis of respondents' perceptions of the variable, job satisfaction influences employee performance. This can be seen from the calculated T-value, which is greater than the T-table, at $3.52 > -1.96$. Therefore, it can be concluded that the influence is significant. Thus, job satisfaction is partially proven to have a positive and significant influence on employee performance, or in other words, Hypothesis 5 (Ha) is accepted. Examples of job satisfaction indicators according to Hasibuan (in Mardiana & Novalia, 2020) that support satisfied employees generally have high commitment, are honest, demonstrate creativity, and maximize their abilities. Furthermore, adequate wages and salaries also increase satisfaction, thus triggering optimal performance. This means that higher job satisfaction, better employee performance. Thus, the research results successfully prove that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia Dept Unit. The results of this study align with those of Nurrohmat & Lestari (2021), who found that Job Satisfaction practices significantly influence Employee Performance.

Job Satisfaction Mediates Work Flexibility and Employee Performance

The sixth hypothesis (Ha) states that the direct effect of Work Flexibility on Employee Performance is $(0.31) \times 100 = 9.61\%$. The indirect effect of Work Flexibility on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction is $0.63 \times 0.59 \times 100 = 21.24\%$. The percentage results above indicate that Work Flexibility can improve Employee Performance both directly and indirectly through Job Satisfaction. Therefore, Job Satisfaction is a mediating variable. Therefore, the research results successfully prove that Job Satisfaction mediates Work Flexibility and Employee Performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia Dept Unit. The results of this study align with those of Huda & Ekhsan (2023), who stated that Job Satisfaction practices mediate Work Flexibility and Employee Performance.

Job Satisfaction Mediates Work Morale and Employee Performance

The seventh hypothesis (Ha) states that the direct effect of Work Morale on Employee Performance is $(-0.65) \times 100 = 42.25\%$. The indirect effect of Work Morale and Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction is $-0.13 \times -0.04 \times 100 = 0.26\%$. The percentage results above indicate that Work Morale can improve Employee Performance both directly and indirectly through Job Satisfaction. Therefore, Job Satisfaction is a mediating variable. Therefore, the research findings successfully prove that Job Satisfaction mediates Work Morale and Employee Performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia Dept. Unit. These results align with those of Ayu et al. (2020), who stated that Job Satisfaction practices mediate Work Morale and Employee Performance.

CONCLUSION

This chapter describes the conclusions that answer the research questions and explain the findings obtained in the study.

Conclusion

1. Work Flexibility has been partially proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at PT XYZ

- Manufacturing Indonesia. This indicates that with appropriate work flexibility, employees will perform well in the company.
2. Work Morale has been partially proven to have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This demonstrates that work morale can influence employee job satisfaction.
 3. Work Flexibility has been partially proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia. This demonstrates that work flexibility can influence employee performance.
 4. Work Morale has been partially proven to have no positive and significant effect on employee performance. This demonstrates that work morale does not influence employee performance.
 5. Job Satisfaction has been partially proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia. This demonstrates that job satisfaction can influence employee performance.
 6. Job satisfaction is proven to mediate the relationship between work flexibility and employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia, as the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect.
 7. Job satisfaction is proven to mediate the relationship between work morale and employee performance at PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia, as the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect.

Recommendations

The results of this study indicate that job satisfaction and work flexibility have a positive and significant impact on employee performance. Therefore, PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia's management is advised to improve employee job satisfaction, including by providing appropriate salaries, creating a comfortable work environment, and providing flexibility in carrying out work. Increased job satisfaction is expected to contribute directly to improved employee performance, in accordance with the indicators identified in this study. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on employee performance, therefore, PT XYZ Manufacturing Indonesia management needs to maintain employee satisfaction. In this study, salary satisfaction is the most dominant indicator in shaping the Job Satisfaction variable.

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